

Deep learning algorithms for scRNAseq analysis have yielded positive results, but there are still more promising ways that need to be developed for regenerative medicine

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Abstract. A detailed survey of the use of many deep learning algorithms on scRNAseq data for regenerative medicine was published in this article. Currently, the best deep learning algorithms for scRNAseq analysis have yielded positive results, but there are still more promising ways that need to be developed to better handle technical noise, account for cell expression variability, identify MSCs, and anticipate stem cell type. To gain access to scRNAseq data, these deep learning techniques need to be paired with scRNAseq data. The ability to identify cell types and functions accurately and fast utilizing these algorithms has not yet been made possible. In the study we conducted, we reached the conclusion that further research has to be done into how to apply deep learning algorithms to interpret scRNAseq data, which may be used to better cell therapy and regenerative medicine efforts.

1. Introduction

The goal of regenerative medicine is to replace nonfunctional or dead cells in order to heal or regenerate tissues and organs, restoring normal function to damaged organs. The use of stem cell transplantation and tissue regeneration procedures in the treatment of various illnesses has expanded dramatically in recent years. 1

With the advancements in stem cell research, cell therapy, the therapeutic approach of introducing new cells into a tissue to treat illnesses, may be able to cure diseases that are resistant to standard treatments. Stem cells are self-renewing and have the ability to develop into a variety of human body cells. As a result, stem cell treatments may have an impact on the area of regenerative medicine. However, contemporary approaches for using stem cells in regenerative medicine and cell therapy are still in their infancy, and most of what is known about the subject is speculative. The regeneration mechanism of transplanted mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) against illnesses, for example, remains unknown. Furthermore, parameters such as tissue source and separation procedure have an impact on MSC differentiation capacity. 2 and 3 There is no agreement on the conventional features of MSC differentiation potential at this time. Because of these ambiguities, we have been unable to evaluate the effectiveness and self-renewal capability of isolated MSC, implying that MSC usage will give results that are entirely different or nearly contrary to the intended value of clinical applications. It is more reliable to identify cell types in stem cells using genomics approaches, such as relying on single cell RNA sequencing (scRNAseq) data to assess and assess gene expression patterns or quantify protein content. As a result, we anticipate that deep learning approaches may be used to evaluate scRNAseq data, forecast cell types, and get a better understanding of MSC differentiation potential and direction. We can directly use stem cell subpopulations with the required differentiation direction for treatment if we can determine what type of cells they can differentiate into before using MSCs, allowing us to treat diseases more directly and achieve precision medical treatment, promoting the development of cell therapy and regenerative medicine.

Our research group has focused on musculoskeletal illness therapies, particularly tendon tissue regeneration techniques including biomaterials, stem cells, and growth factor delivery systems. We believe ourselves to be a well-established group in the field of tendon tissue engineering and regeneration, including publications on the use of stem cells and biomaterials in tendon tissue engineering. We propose that machine learning approaches

such as deep learning be used to examine the scRNAseq data set and generate predictions about hidden subpopulations in the cell population. This allows researchers to accurately analyze MSCs and employ the subpopulations identified based on differentiation potential for stem cell therapy and regenerative medicine treatments.

The previously published remarks mainly describe the use of machine learning techniques on genomics data, 4-9, or the use of more specialized machine learning techniques on scRNAseq data, 10-12, or the use of deep learning methods on genomics data.

This review summarized the various algorithms of deep learning methods applied to scRNAseq data in this review, discussed the impact of their combination on the development of stem cell therapy and regenerative medicine, and proposed additional algorithmic suggestions for future cell therapy development.

2. Scrnaseq Introduction

Previously, people analyzed the whole genome sequence information of mixed DNA samples of millions or more of cells, and the result was usually only the average value of the signals in a certain group of cells or the most dominant cells, ignoring the characteristics of a single cell or a small subset of cells. For example, if we wish to analyze a specific tissue using whole genome sequence information in the hopes of finding a small number of altered cells (perhaps early cancer cells), it will be very difficult since the features of a small number of cells would be overlooked.

However, single-cell sequencing technologies can help to overcome this issue. The Singlecell sequencing technique is more precise than typical whole genome sequencing technology, especially at the level of gene expression. Furthermore, single-cell sequencing can discover a small quantity of gene expression or other uncommon RNA. The Singlecell sequencing technique produces omnidirectional and multilayer results, which greatly aids our knowledge of cells, tissues, and human systems.

scRNAseq revolutionized transcriptome research. Andrews and Hemberg compiled a list of single-cell isolation procedures and scRNAseq approaches that are now accessible, including quality control, dimensionality reduction, cell clustering, trajectory inference, gene regulatory network reconstruction, and so on, in 2018. 15

At the moment, scientists have proposed a number of ways to reveal the spatial structure of cells by combining single-cell transcriptomics with spatial transcriptomics. Moncada et al presented a technique for multimodal intersection analysis by combining the two omics mentioned above. 16 They discovered that using this strategy, they can map cell types, cell subgroups, and even cell states in space. Peng et al. have published a review on the use of scRNAseq and spatial transcriptomics to better understand stem cell lineage features throughout early embryonic development. 17

scRNAseq data, on the other hand, contains more noise and greater dimensions than bulk RNAseq data and is more complicated due to technological restrictions and biological considerations. As a result, many strategies for assessing bulk RNAseq data are ineffective when applied to scRNAseq data. To evaluate the scRNAseq data, users must either develop the algorithm or tweak the current method. As a result, various methods for analyzing and interpreting scRNAseq data have been developed in recent years, but the findings show that unique techniques are still needed to assure the accuracy and repeatability of the results, and deep learning will be a viable choice. From the standpoint of applying deep learning algorithms to scRNAseq data, this review will examine the influence of deep learning on stem cell treatment and regenerative medicine.

3. Deep Learning Technologies Introduction

Machine learning is a technique for predicting unknown facts by automatically analyzing and extracting laws from data. The appeal of bioinformatics resides in their capacity to forecast models without a thorough knowledge of the model's core process, which is obviously appealing to most biologists who are not mathematicians. Machine learning technologies, such as t distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (tSNE) and high-latitude data visualizations¹⁸, provide analytic approaches for genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, among other fields.

Extracting, converting, and loading source data; data preprocessing; feature extraction; model training; cross validation; fresh data prediction are the six processes in a typical machine learning workflow. Typically, the input data sample is assigned to x (perhaps a vector), and the output data sample is assigned to y . (maybe a single number).

The standard procedure for machine learning

Machine learning algorithms, unlike previous algorithms that need domain expertise and stringent model assumptions, can automatically discover data and anticipate model structure. As a result, machine learning techniques are well suited to data-driven science, particularly in genomics. 5 The ability of machine learning algorithms is primarily determined by how each feature is captured or calculated. 14

Artificial neural networks research gave rise to the notion of deep learning. A deep learning structure is a multilayer perceptron with numerous hidden layers. By integrating low-level features to identify dispersed feature representations of data, deep learning creates a more abstract high-level representation of attribute category or feature. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) and deep belief networks are two types of deep learning technologies (DBN).

CNN can readily extract certain local relevance characteristics using convolution kernels, is adaptable to data transformations, and has a generally positive effect on pictures. The CNN algorithm may be used to improve the accuracy of segmentation of cell pictures. 19 CNN may also be used in conjunction with scRNAseq data to infer gene relationships. 20 DBN is based on Bayesian reasoning and finds the joint probability distribution of the data to automatically retrieve the high-level information concealed in the data that is difficult to explain. Its output information gives the data a distinct personality. Based on the DBN framework, Chen et al built a Bayesian network model for the interaction between distinct histone modifications across neighboring nucleosomes. It was discovered that nucleosome communication plays a key role in signal propagation, chromatin remodeling, and transcriptional control. 21 Deep learning's application in DNA sequence data was also demonstrated in a groundbreaking study in 2015. 22 Since then, the number of studies relating to deep learning's application in genomics has risen. The use of deep learning to scRNAseq data will be discussed in this paper.

4. Discussion

All genes are included in the scRNAseq findings, which are valuable for cell and tissue analysis. Machine learning approaches are now commonly utilized to evaluate scRNAseq data¹⁵, such as recognizing cells, detecting novel cell kinds, and generating pedigree trees. However, when studying various sorts of data sets, the explanations and answers provided by these approaches are not always sufficient, and there is presently no approach that can be used to analyze all distinct sorts of cells. Furthermore, the dimensionality of the collected data is increasing as a result of the in-depth investigation of the cells. Ordinary machine learning algorithms are unable to tackle difficulties created by high dimensions, and forced dimensionality reduction will result in data loss. Then deep learning entered the picture. Deep learning, for example, can analyze high-dimensional data without losing data information by using tensors (various directions in the tensor represent various data kinds). Deep learning technology, as we all know, is very scalable and can predict unknown variables based on provided data, which is very useful in the field of single-cell genomics. For example, with an existing single cell type database of a certain organization, one may train and obtain a model, and then forecast if an unknown cell belongs to the tissue or which cell type in the tissue. This is critical for the successful implementation of stem cell treatment.

Deep learning may also be used for unsupervised learning. They learn from unlabeled scRNAseq data to provide a data-driven definition of cell kind and identity. This is useful for studying data sets where labels are difficult to come by. Unsupervised algorithms may also be utilized to combine scRNAseq data from diverse sources, according to Shaham et al.²³. 25, 24 The constant expansion of similar tissue data sets, as we know from the "Human Cell Atlas Project," 26 makes this more and more significant, which is critical for the fulfillment of stem cell treatment applications. Despite the capability of scRNAseq, single-cell sequencing data is sometimes plagued by issues such as excessive deletion and noise. The transcript will be lost during the reverse transcription process due to the tiny number. As a result of this condition, "dropout" occurrences occurred. According to Kharchenko et al, just a tiny portion of each cell's transcriptome was recognized during the sequencing step,²⁷ and these issues will result in a sparse gene expression matrix. This is a typical issue with lowly expressed genes. However, omitting these genes from the study completely isn't the most effective strategy. This method would squander much too much valuable data, such as transcription factors and surface indicators.

As a result, more effective attribution procedures are needed to recover the lost gene expression in the scRNAseq data set in order to acquire more exact gene expression measurement findings. Many approaches for attributing scRNAseq data have been proposed earlier, according to Arisdakessian et al, including MAGIC,²⁹ ScImpute,³⁰ SAVER,³¹ and DrImpute. 32 However, these approaches take a long time to execute, which

makes them unsuitable for use in the ever-expanding scRNAseq data set.

Then, Arisdakessian et al presented DeepImpute, a deep neural network-based interpolation technique that employs a dropout layer and loss function to learn data patterns for interpolation. 28 This strategy minimizes complexity by breaking down issues into smaller chunks and finetuning the subneural network, or by building many subneural networks to estimate genes in a divide-and-conquer approach. In their paper, Arisdakessian et al claimed that if accuracy is measured using Pearson's correlation coefficient or mean square error, DeepImpute is more accurate on experimental data than many other scRNAseq interpolation methods (such as SAVER, MAGIC, VIPER, and DCA), and DeepImpute is faster and uses less memory than those methods. 28

Arisdakessian et al used four publicly accessible scRNAseq data sets to demonstrate the benefits of DeepImpute: two cell lines, Jurkat and 293T (10X Genomic); one mouse interfollicular epidermis data set released in GSE67602; and one mouse neuron cell data set (10X Genomic). 28 Simultaneously, they hypothesized that the DeepImpute approach may do cluster analysis or differential expression (DE) analysis on actual or simulated data sets, hence improving downstream analysis outcomes. In sum, Arisdakessian et al think that DeepImpute is suited for processing the ever-increasing number of interpolation techniques for scRNAseq data because of its accuracy, speed, and scalability.

In comparison to the DeepImpute approach, Mongia et al introduced deepMc, a deep matrix factorization-based attribution system. 33 The deepMc approach makes no assumptions about the distribution of gene expression. A matrix is used to generate a depth model and then decomposed into several matrices for further analysis using matrix decomposition or kernel specification minimization. This approach adds to the variety of interpolation problem-solving options. DeepMc does not require any hyperparameters; all it requires is a parameter that may also pass the estimated theory. This is in stark contrast to conventional deep learning models, which need a significant amount of effort to fine-tune parameters. Mongia et al. demonstrated that the deepMc approach outperforms the DeepImpute attribution technique in the majority of testing scenarios. We all know that one of the most important uses of scRNAseq is to discover distinct cell types from diverse cell populations, so the two can be compared based on the clustering accuracy obtained after imputation. DeepMc has a substantially greater accuracy than DeepImpute in terms of the Adjusted Rand Index value achieved after using kmeans clustering following various interpolation approaches. 33 Second, they evaluated the accuracy of DE analysis to compare the two approaches. They employed the receiver's operating characteristic curve's area under the curve value, and deepMc is more accurate than DeepImpute. Furthermore, starting with cell type separability (CTS).

As a result, the deepMc approach may be recommended while tackling the interpolation problem of restoring lost gene expression. Of course, the DeepImpute technique offers advantages of its own.

Data from single-cell transcriptomes can reveal previously unknown biodiversity. In practice, numerous studies are required to fully utilize the scRNAseq technique in order to determine cell lineages and real transcription signals. We must employ various strategies to adjust the batch effect in the scRNAseq data due to the combined data.

ScVI may be used to standardize and evaluate scRNAseq data since it is a completely probabilistic approach based on probability Bayesian theory and establishing conditional distributions using deep neural networks. 24 To gather information between comparable cells and genes, this technique uses deep neural networks and random optimization. It takes into account not just the data's sensitivity, but also the effects of batch processing, allowing the findings to more accurately approximate the distribution of observed expression levels. scVI delivers great accuracy in batch effect correction, cell clustering, differential expression, and other areas. 24 After using the scVI technique for clustering, it was discovered that the subgroups that were previously "hidden" owing to the clustering method's inaccuracy, scVI and other techniques (SIMLR, 23 MNNs 34 [Mutual Nearest Neighbor] + PCA [Principal Components Analysis]) had been annotated. 10 On the above-mentioned data set, a cell clustering analysis was done. The results reveal that scVI can capture the hierarchical structure between cell subsets more precisely and uncover cell subsets that are "hidden groups" for other approaches. Similarly, we can identify what sorts of cells the stem cells can develop into before utilizing them if we learn from the stem cell data set and then apply the learned model to the unknown group of stem cells. As a result, stem cell subsets with the needed differentiation direction may be employed for treatment directly, allowing for more direct treatment of illnesses, precision medicine, and the advancement of cell therapy and regenerative medicine.

BERMUDA (using deep autoencoders for batch effect removal) is a new approach for correcting batch effects in scRNAseq data based on transfer learning. 35 The "domain adaptive learning" approach is used to translate the original data to the new feature space (in the target domain) by picking an appropriate feature representation,

ensuring that the distribution of the source domain and the target domain in the new feature space are as similar as feasible. BERMUDA can cluster the cells and remove the errors produced by the batch effect. When a clustering mistake occurs, cells from the acinar group, for example, are associated with cells from the endothelial group. The analysis that follows will be altered as well. There might be a significant disconnect, if not outright disagreement, between the connection with the real cells.

Wang et al demonstrated that BERMUDA outperforms scVI in handling batch effects on publically accessible human pancreatic datasets obtained using various scRNAseq techniques. 35 They assess BERMUDA using biological data. They tested it on datasets from the human pancreas obtained using several scRNAseq techniques that are publically available. "Muraro batch" 36 is one data set, whereas "Baron batch" is another. 37 To imitate the significant disparities in cell type distribution reported in true scRNAseq data, they utilized all of the cells from these two batches and then removed alpha and beta cells from the Baron group.

Batch effects in pancreatic cell scRNAseq data are removed. Experiment all on pancreatic data set UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection) representations of batch effect reduction outcomes. Dashed circles indicate identified alpha and beta cell subpopulations in the Baron batch. With permission from Genome Biology, reprinted from Wang et al³⁵. singlecell RNA sequencing (scRNAseq)

When just batch effects are selected, the BERMUDA technique is better suited, as seen in the above comparison. scVI is, of course, a fantastic candidate for other downstream analyses as well.

To find the optimum batch corrector space, scVI mostly depends on similarities between individual cells, and these similarities do not fully use the clustering structure of distinct cell populations. To eliminate batch effects, BERMUDA employs data similarity between cell clusters. Because clustering and batch effect removal are linked, the best batch effect elimination approach should be used in conjunction with clustering. It's also envisaged that there will be a means to analyze all batches of cells at the same time. For scRNAseq analysis, Li et al presented the DESC technique, which is an unsupervised deep learning system that can iteratively learn clusterspecific gene expression representations and cluster assignments. 38 DESC will gradually reduce batch effects in iterations as long as the technical difference between batches is lower than the genuine biological difference (e.g., the difference between cell types). DESC provides a greater and more stable clustering accuracy than the scVI and BERMUDA approaches.

Furthermore, scAlign³⁹ is an unsupervised deep learning approach for cell label sets that can combine partial, overlapping, or complete cell label sets and estimate the per-cell gene expression differential across the full data set.

ScAlign conducts unit comparison in a single data set by learning a two-way mapping (between the low-dimensional comparison space and the sorting unit). Then, in the low-dimensional comparison space, scAlign completes the grouping of units by function and type. This allows for the correct marking of fresh data sets that lack annotation labels, as well as the detection of unusual cell populations. ScAlign's neural network design helps it and allows it to increase its alignment capabilities. 39 scAlign outperforms existing comparison approaches such as scmap,⁴⁰ scVI,²⁴ and Seurat, according to Johansen and Quon. 41

We can better perform downstream analysis on the scRNAseq data, complete cell categorization, and uncover novel cell subgroups after correcting the batch effect in the scRNAseq data. When utilized in a variety of fundamental analytical tasks, such as batch correction, visualization, grouping, and differential expression, scVI has demonstrated great accuracy. 24 This enables us to better define the sorts of stem cells that will be employed in clinical trials, as well as the types of cells that they can develop into and the stem cell subgroups that have differentiation potential. It is critical that we deploy stem cell treatment in clinical settings and achieve the intended outcomes. We expect that combining deep learning and scRNAseq data can enhance cell therapy and regenerative medicine implementation, as well as affect precision medicine implementation.

Of course, the deep learning method can not only remove the batch effect in scRNAseq data or complete cell clustering, but it can also learn the data's inherent biological modules, describe the biologically meaningful control data set modules, and provide information about which modules are active for each unit.

The autoencoder, for example, after deconvolution processing,⁴² It also adapts well to a significant amount of "lost" data, which is valuable and crucial for processing scRNAseq data. Following deconvolution of the resultant model, Kinalis et al discovered that the autoencoder may build a relationship between the model's presentation layer and biological processes after specialized training. The autoencoder completes the signature

decryption of genes or places by mapping the hidden cells in the model to well-defined modules, allowing the autoencoder to better delineate the driving mechanisms behind a specific cellular impact. 42 This will allow us to look at the stem cell population from a different perspective, allowing us to screen the subpopulations of stem cells we require and driving the development of stem cell therapy.

The algorithms listed below have aided in the advancement of stem cell treatment in some way. They don't utilize scRNAseq to cluster cells directly; instead, they look at cells from several angles, such as cell contact, quantification of certain subgroups, and tissue dependant status, or predicting the abundance of surface proteins on the scRNAseq data set.

The CNNC algorithm was proposed by Yuan and BarJoseph. 20 They analyze the scRNAseq data using the CNN method, which can conduct causal inference, illness gene prediction, function allocation, and other operations on the data. Because CNN can readily extract some local related features using the convolution kernel, which has a stronger influence on the picture, this approach turns expression data that lacks locality into an image for later processing. The technique then uses a supervised methodology to make genetic connection inferences. To use CNNC, Yuan and BarJoseph employed a significant quantity of single cell expression data and tested it on a variety of inference tasks. In terms of inferring function allocation, gene interaction, and causality inference, they found that CNNC outperforms earlier techniques (DNN, count statistics, mutual information).

Furthermore, DigitalDLorter is a deep learning algorithm that can forecast the fraction of each cell type in a huge number of RNA sequencing data. 43-267 The immunological infiltration of colorectal cancer and breast cancer in bulk RNAseq samples is enumerated and quantified using scRNAseq data. It adjusts the composition of any cell type specified based on scRNAseq data using a deep neural network (DNN) model, allowing it to measure not just traditional cell categories like lymphocytes, but also particular subgroups and tissue-dependent states. It differs from the previous technique in that it takes into account the microenvironment's effect on the transcriptome. The physiological status of cells will be more precisely quantified and defined as a result of this. When we employ stem cell treatment, this introduces new considerations.

You may utilize a deep neural network-based transfer learning algorithm, cTPnet,44 to use existing single-cell multiomics resources to predict the surface protein abundance of scRNAseq data in addition to assessing cell information from scRNAseq data alone. The results of Zhou et al indicate that cTPnet can predict the abundance of surface proteins on the scRNAseq data set using the REAPseq and CITEseq data sets, as well as the absence of cell type data in the training data set, using the REAPseq and CITEseq data sets. 44 Furthermore, cTPnet can learn from healthy cells and then infer the immunological profile of malignant cells, which is critical for our stem cell treatment prediction.

The increased use of scRNAseq technology has given us a better knowledge of cell heterogeneity at the transcriptional level, and it has transformed the way individuals evaluate and extract meaningful information from bulk RNA. Despite the high expense of scRNAseq, we can extract a lot of useful information from scRNAseq data. This data is extensive and multilayered, allowing us to gain a thorough understanding of cells, tissues, and human bodies. Now, researchers frequently employ various approaches to reanalyze the published data set in order to verify the algorithm's correctness or to identify previously overlooked information in the published data set using a validated new technique. However, evaluating scRNAseq data is difficult in general since the data is noisy, has a high dimensionality, and has high variability, and there is no difference when evaluating it. As a result, users must select an appropriate tool for analysis based on the nature and distribution of their input data collection, as well as the study's unique aim.

Deep learning algorithms are unquestionably a suitable choice for analyzing scRNAseq data since they can handle high-dimensional data well. Because scRNAseq data includes the genome derived from the same cell, the appearance group, and transcriptome and proteome data, deep learning methods have a number of benefits. For example, endtoend learning may enhance prediction accuracy, and it can also efficiently analyze multiplex data. Multimodal modeling allows for the examination of several data sources, resulting in a more complete and precise trained model. People will be able to combine scRNAseq data with spatial transcriptomic data in the future to understand cellular information in a multidimensional fashion using deep learning. Furthermore, by abstracting many mathematical and technological elements, the deep learning framework lowers the entry barriers for constructing new models. This is due to the fact that most biomedical researchers do not have enough time to understand mathematics or computer science theory, let alone build or construct a new model. Using the proper method to evaluate the scRNAseq data can help us forecast the type of cell subpopulation or uncommon cell population with more accuracy.

We all know that stem cells, particularly MSC, have tremendous medicinal potential and might be crucial in the treatment or cure of a variety of disorders. Isolated MSCs, on the other hand, have a distinct effectiveness and self-renewal capability. If they are used directly in clinical practice, they are likely to produce discrepancies, if not outright opposing results, between expectations and actual results. However, if people can use appropriate methods to accurately predict the types of stem cell subpopulations, the cure rate will also improve when using MSC for stem cell therapy, allowing people to better use cell therapy and regenerative medicine strategies to treat various diseases and structural injuries. Humanity will gain from the use of this exact medicinal procedure. Finally, we expect that combining deep learning and scRNAseq data will enhance cell therapy and regenerative medicine implementation, as well as have an impact on precision medicine implementation.

5. Conclusion

The application of several deep learning approaches to scRNAseq data was summarized in this review. While the current deep learning approaches for scRNAseq analysis are promising, improved tools are still required to effectively deal with technical noise, account for cell expression variability, assess MSCs, and forecast stem cell type. Furthermore, using these deep learning algorithms with scRNAseq data to reliably and quickly identify the kind and function of each cell is not yet viable. We came to the conclusion that more research into how to apply deep learning algorithms to analyze scRNAseq data is necessary since it can improve cell therapy and regenerative medicine efforts.

References

1. Abdelhamid, H. N., M. Dowaidar, M. Hällbrink, and Ü. Langel. 2019. "Cell Penetrating Peptides-Hierarchical Porous Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks Nanoparticles: An Efficient Gene Delivery Platform." *SSRN Electron. J.* https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3435895.
2. Abdelhamid, Hani Nasser, Moataz Dowaidar, Mattias Hällbrink, and Ülo Langel. 2020. "Gene Delivery Using Cell Penetrating Peptides-Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks." *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials: The Official Journal of the International Zeolite Association* 300 (June): 110173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2020.110173>.
3. Abdelhamid, Hani Nasser, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ülo Langel. 2020. "Carbonized Chitosan Encapsulated Hierarchical Porous Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks Nanoparticles for Gene Delivery." *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials: The Official Journal of the International Zeolite Association* 302 (August): 110200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2020.110200>.
4. Ahmad, Almeman, Khalaf Hassan, Rasool Semaab, Moataz Dowaidar, and Al Orainy Mohammad. 2013. "The Impact of CYP2C19 Polymorphism on Platelet Reactivity for Guiding Clopidogrel Treatment and Cost Analysis." *Journal of the Saudi Heart Association* 25 (2): 107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsha.2013.03.005>.
5. Algahsham, Abdullah, Ahmad A. A. Settin, Ahmad Ali, and Hisham Ismail. n.d. "Association of MTHFR C677T and A1298C Polymorphisms with Hypertension among Saudi Subjects from Qassim Region." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 6 (1). Accessed June 18, 2021. <http://ijhs.org.sa/index.php/journal/article/view/312>.
6. Algasham, Abdullah, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ahmad A. Settin. 2011. "Methylenetetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) and Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene Polymorphisms among Saudi Population from Qassim Region." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 5 (2 Suppl 1): 3–4. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23284552>.
7. Alghasham, Abdullah, Ahmad Ali, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ahmad A. Settin. 2012. "CYP2J2 -50 G/T and ADRB2 G46A Gene Polymorphisms in Saudi Subjects with Hypertension." *Genetic Testing and Molecular Biomarkers* 16 (9): 1027–31. <https://doi.org/10.1089/gtmb.2012.0006>.
8. Alghasham, Abdullah, Ahmad A. Settin, Ahmad Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, and Hisham Ismail. 2012a. "Association of MTHFR C677T and A1298C Gene Polymorphisms with Hypertension." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 6 (1): 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0005968>.
9. Moataz Dowaidar. 2012b. "Association of MTHFR C677T and A1298C Gene Polymorphisms with Hypertension." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 6 (1): 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0005968>.
10. Ali, Ahmad, Abdullah Alghasham, Hisham Ismail, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ahmad Settin. 2013. "ACE I/D and eNOS E298D Gene Polymorphisms in Saudi Subjects with Hypertension." *Journal of the Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System: JRAAS* 14 (4): 348–53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470320312459976>.
11. Ali, Ahmed A. A., Nahla M. Wassim, Moataz M. Dowaidar, and Ahmed E. Yaseen. 2013a. "Genetic Polymorphism of CYP2D6 Gene among Egyptian Hypertensive Cases." *The Journal of Basic & Applied Zoology* 66 (4): 228–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobaz.2012.12.002>.
12. Ali, Ahmed A. A., Nahla M. Wassim, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ahmed E. Yaseen. 2013b. "Association

- of eNOS (E298D) and CYP2J2 (-50G/T) Gene Polymorphisms with Hypertension among Egyptian Cases.” *The Journal of Basic & Applied Zoology* 66 (4): 234–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobaz.2012.12.001>.
13. Moataz Dowaidar. 2013c. “Association of eNOS (E298D) and CYP2J2 (-50G/T) Gene Polymorphisms with Hypertension among Egyptian Cases.” *The Journal of Basic & Applied Zoology* 66 (4): 234–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobaz.2012.12.001>.
 14. Aljarallah, Badr, Ahmed Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ahmad Settin. 2011. “Prevalence of α -1-Antitrypsin Gene Mutations in Saudi Arabia.” *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology: Official Journal of the Saudi Gastroenterology Association* 17 (4): 256–60. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1319-3767.82580>.
 15. Dowaidar, M., J. Regberg, D. A. Dobchev, and T. Lehto. 2017. “Refinement of a Quantitative Structure–activity Relationship Model for Prediction of Cell-Penetrating Peptide Based Transfection Systems.” *International Journal of*. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s10989-016-9542-8.pdf>.
 16. Dowaidar, Moataz. 2017. “In-Silico Design of Peptide-Based Transfection Systems, in-Vitro Validation, and up-Take Pathways Investigation.” Department of Neurochemistry, Stockholm University.
 17. Moataz Dowaidar. 2018. “Chimeric Gene Delivery Vectors : Design, Synthesis, and Mechanisms from Transcriptomics Analysis.” Department of Biochemistry and Biophysics, Stockholm University. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1242000>.
 18. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021a. “Cardiometabolic Conditions Could Be Related to Vitamin D Deficiency. The Genetic Determinants That Affect Vitamin D Pathways May Be Solved with Nanomedicines.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/nqewr>.
 19. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021b. “Different Insulin Resistance and Inflammation Pathways Are Influenced by Genetic Factors in Metabolic Syndrome. Gene Therapy Enables Early Recognition and Treatment of the Genetic Factors.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gqwj2>.
 20. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021c. “Gene Therapy Has Been Shown to Be Valuable for Understanding Complex Disease Pathophysiologies. The Medical Profession as a Whole Will Have to Invest in Specialized Investigations.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8fg9y>.
 21. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021d. “Genetic and Epigenetic Discoveries Hold Promising Avenues in Cardiovascular Prevention and Management (CVDs). Key Nucleic Acids Are Being Researched and Developed for Medicinal Use.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hk7pe>.
 22. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021e. “Genome Editing Can Now Be Carried out in an Isogenic Setting. It Can Be Effectively Transmitted to Somatic Tissues in Mice, but Not to Humans. Despite These Doubts, CRIS Has Great Potential as a Medical Promise.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4rn3v>.
 23. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021f. “Genome-Wide Association Experiments Have Uncovered a Slew of Cardiometabolic Trait-Associated Variants. This Information Can Be Useful in the Implementation of New Diagnostic and Treatment Strategies.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4vws8>.
 24. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021g. “Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) Have Revolutionized Our View of Human Health and Disease Genetics and Offered Novel Gene Therapy Targets.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/rvm3z>.
 25. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021h. “Metabolic Syndrome_ the Presence of Inflammatory Mechanisms in Abdominal Obesity Is Undeniable, Gene Therapy Using Nanoparticles and Adenoviruses Technologies Is Promising.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2j5xt>.
 26. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021i. “miRNAs May Be Used as Preventive Agents for Metabolic Diseases in the near Future. Understanding the Interplay between pro-Adipogenic_ and Anti-Ad Pipogenic miRNA’ Could Lead to New Biomarkers.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3dr8c>.
 27. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021j. “Nanomedicine Has Elegantly Attempted to Cure Multiple Gene Polymorphisms and Mutations in Cardiovascular Diseases Using Gene Therapy Techniques.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/d3x8g>.
 28. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021k. “Thrombosis Pathways and Therapeutic Strategies.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/57vyz>.
 29. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021l. “What Genomic Research Has Told Us about the Obesity and Its Possible Gene Therapy Targets.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ym49s>.
 30. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021m. “Exosomes Can Make the Use of Circulating miRNA as a Biomarker More Feasible. The Aim of Gene Therapy Should Be to Learn Everything There Is to Know about miRNA Activity.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/edkua>.
 31. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021n. “Anti-Sense Pathways Have Been Generated Using siRNA. The Liver and Other Often Used Organs Will Now Be Targeted.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m6xvp>.
 32. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021o. “CrisPR/CRIS Systems Are Highly Effective and Useful for Genomic

- Manipulation. Despite This, Cardiac Treatment Remains Difficult due to Existing Genome Editing and Delivery Processes.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3nwzd>.
33. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021p. “Discoveries in Gene-Environment Interactions That Influence CVD, Lipid Traits, Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension Appear to Be Able to Influence Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cr5af>.
 34. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021q. “Genome Editing’s Potential Target Diseases in the Cardiovascular Field.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gc23p>.
 35. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021r. “Key Genetic Factors in the Metabolic Syndrome Predisposition Which May Be a Therapeutic Options by Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/f38sk>.
 36. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021s. “miRNA Can Be a Part of Both the Onset and Cure of Coronary Heart Disease.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/teqh8>.
 37. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021t. “Preclinical Studies and Clinical Trials Have Sparked Interest in Certain Biological Medications for Atherosclerotic Coronary Heart Disease.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ts8mh>.
 38. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021u. “Researchers Would Be Able to Develop a Detailed Picture of Chromatin in Disease, Which Would Be Useful for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9z48>.
 39. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021v. “The Cardiometabolic-Based Chronic Disease Model Lays the Foundations for Accurate, Evidence-Based Preventive Targeting and Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/up9z4>.
 40. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021w. “2D MOFs Have Unique Features for Biological Applications. They Can Be Utilized for Gene Therapy, Bioimaging, Biosensing, Photodynamic Therapy, and Tissue Engineering.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4q9ct>.
 41. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021x. “3D Bioprinting for Enhanced Vascularization, and Gene Editing to Provide a More Favorable Immunological Response Are Just Some of the Potential Uses of Carbon Materials.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/v2xy8>.
 42. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021y. “Anderson–Fabry Disease Can Be a Target for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tcgka>.
 43. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021z. “Antisense Oligonucleotides (ASOs) and CRISPR Systems Are Promising Gene Therapy Treatments for Alzheimer’s Disease.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ws796>.
 44. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021aa. “Any Alteration in PPAR Genomic Sequence, Splicing Pattern, or PTM Is Likely to Cause Major Alterations in Its Function. In Personalized Medicine, Such Data Becomes More Significant in Gene Therapy Design.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/y8n79>.
 45. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ab. “Applying Genome-Wide Association Technology to Brain Diseases Enables the Discovery of lncRNAs Targets for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hm4eu>.
 46. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ac. “Autophagy and Proteostasis Adjustment Role in Normal Brain Function and Neurodegenerative Disorders.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m4yra>.
 47. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ad. “Basal Ganglia-Cerebellar and Brainstem-Cerebellar Circuits May Interact Improperly with Dystonia. Linking Network Disruptions to Cell Failure Will Enable Understanding Pathophysiology and Designing Gene Therapy Methods.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8w35s>.
 48. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ae. “Blood Products Are Used to Treat a Multitude of Diseases, so the Blood Transfusion System Needs to Be Enhanced. CRISPR/Cas9 Has Made It Viable to Make HLA Class I-Deleted Blood Products to Avoid Rejection.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/egr3n>.
 49. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021af. “Calixarenes (CAs) Are Promising in Biomedicine, Biosensing, Bioimaging and Gene Delivery Systems.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/n9vjy>.
 50. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ag. “CAR T Cell Research Has Quickly Advanced from the Bench to the Clinic and Back. The Results of the Trials Have Revealed New Mechanisms.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/f9wm7>.
 51. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ah. “CAR T-Cell Treatment Remains Clinically Challenging. Therapeutic Strategies May Be Designed to Cut off Immunotherapy Utilizing Safety Switches.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/s7x4y>.
 52. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ai. “Central Nervous System Gene Therapy Has Entered a New Development Paradigm. New Techniques Are Being Employed for a Wide Range of Illness Indications and Pathways.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/j49wz>.
 53. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021aj. “Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Condition (COPD) Is a Prevalent, Preventable, and Curable Illness with Persistent Respiratory Symptoms and Airflow Limitation.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/vkdut>.
 54. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ak. “CircRNAs Have the Potential to Aid in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Lipid Diseases.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/y3hp4>.
 55. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021al. “Clinical Symptoms, Underlying Pathogenesis, and the Prospect of Tailored Therapies Have All Benefited from Genetic Discoveries in Parkinson’s Disease.”

- <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pdzqb>.
56. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021am. “Code Distribution of siRNA for Cancer Genes such as p53 and Bcl2 Family Genes Has Demonstrated Efficacy in Killing Cancer Cells. Nanoparticles Can Produce a Surface Where Numerous Drugs May Be Coupled, Allowing Combinatory Treatment.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hvcse>.
 57. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021an. “Cognitive Deficiencies Pathophysiology Are Mainly an Unknown Area. Curing the Neurological Conditions Could Be an Objective for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/23xf8>.
 58. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ao. “CRISPR-Based Gene Editing Is Presently Being Tried in Many Clinical Trials.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qbngx>.
 59. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ap. “CRISPR–Cas9 Gene Editing as a Tool for Developing Immunotherapy for Cancer.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dvr4t>.
 60. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021aq. “CRISPR/Cas System Research Has Advanced Significantly in Biological sciences. There Are Still Many Challenges to Effective Delivery before Efficient Gene Editing May Be Achieved.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mc26v>.
 61. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ar. “CRISPR/Cas9 Genome Editing Technology Applications in Biological and Biomedical Fields.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ctqbe>.
 62. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021as. “Critical Limb Ischemia Potential Gene Therapy Strategies.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/aqcpt>.
 63. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021at. “Deep Learning Algorithms for scRNAseq Analysis Have Yielded Positive Results, but There Are Still More Promising Ways That Need to Be Developed for Regenerative Medicine.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dh2pt>.
 64. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021au. “Depression May Be Epigenetically Controlled by miRNAs Making It a Diagnostic or Gene Therapy Target.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fw65m>.
 65. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021av. “Dermatophytes: Role of Host Genetics in the Development of Illness.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mf3bu>.
 66. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021aw. “Developments in Biomedical Technology Will Increase the Importance of mRNA in Treating Brain Tumors, as Well as Other Malignancies.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tvj5x>.
 67. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ax. “Downstream Processing of Virus, Virus-like Particles and Nanoparticulate Inclusion Bodies to Be Used as Gene Delivery Vehicles for Human Gene Therapy Applications.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/exa3q>.
 68. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ay. “Dravet Syndrome Is a Severe Developmental and Epileptic Encephalopathy. Fenfluramine and Gene Therapy Are Promising.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zvq8y>.
 69. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021az. “Exosomes’ Function in Cardiovascular Protection and Neovascularization Implies That They Might Be Used to Treat Ischemia and Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Diseases.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2h8c7>.
 70. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ba. “Ferroposis Cell Death Can Cause Complications That May Be Difficult to Detect and Quantify: Autophagy Role and Possible Therapeutics.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zd2jg>.
 71. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bb. “Following the Discovery of Anti-MDA5 Ab, the Clinical Understanding of Dermatomyositis Has Been Improved.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/jt5f>.
 72. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bc. “For the Treatment of Cystic Fibrosis, RNA Medicines, Gene Transfer Therapies, and Gene Editing Treatments Have Potential.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6afzm>.
 73. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bd. “Frontotemporal Dementia Is a Complex Disorder with a Wide Spectrum of Clinical Symptoms. Personalized Medicine and Gene Therapy Are Promising Strategies for Treatment.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gh4x7>.
 74. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021be. “G6PD Deficiency Is a Common Genetic Trait That Can Protect Heterozygotes from Dying from Malaria.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/g2kza>.
 75. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bf. “Gastric Cancer Is the World’s Second-Largest Death Cause. Peptides Can Be Used to Deliver Radiation or Other Fatal Chemicals to Tumors.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/eu5mj>.
 76. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bg. “Gene Doping May Be Possible for Lifestyle Enhancement.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8xkm5>.
 77. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bh. “Gene Expression Assays Gather Evidence That They Can Provide Useful Therapeutic Information in Young Women.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/d372s>.
 78. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bi. “Gene Therapy and Genome-Editing Treatments That Can Protect Patients from Coronary Artery Disease Are under Investigation.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xqgf8>.
 79. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bj. “Gene Therapy Approaches for Hemophilia A and B.”

- <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ufc4g>.
80. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bk. "Gene Therapy for the Central Nervous System Has Been Initiated. This Expansion Will Require Some Degree of Simplicity in Delivery Processes." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hdy5q>.
 81. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bl. "Gene Therapy for the Treatment of Spinal Muscular Atrophy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kpz5f>.
 82. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bm. "Gene Therapy May Benefit Inherited Ichthyoses with Concurrent Fungal Infections and Severe Ichthyoidoses." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zxmun>.
 83. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bn. "Gene Therapy May Target APOE for Alzheimer's Disease." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3y52k>.
 84. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bo. "Gene Therapy Promises Accurate, Targeted Administration and Overcoming Drug Resistance in Diverse Cancer Cells." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/j34n6>.
 85. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bp. "Gene Therapy Targeting FVIII, FIX for Haemophilia Treatment." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qcbwp>.
 86. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bq. "Gene Therapy Targeting PRMT5 May Be Useful in Immunotherapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gkw8j>.
 87. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021br. "Gene Therapy Using Extracellular Vesicles Loaded with miRNA Derived from Bone Marrow Mesenchymal Stem Cells Is a Cell-Free Medication Delivery Method Used in a Variety of Diseases." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3znvw>.
 88. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bs. "Genetic Engineered MSCs Are Attractive Possibilities for Regenerative Stem-Cell Therapy to Treat Several Liver Diseases." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4cfrd>.
 89. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bt. "Genetic Variants Shared between Alzheimer's Disease and Parkinson's Disease Have Been Discovered in Blood and Brain Samples. Somatic Mosaicism Might Function as an Accelerator." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tr58n>.
 90. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bu. "Genome-Wide Association Studies Promise to Discover Novel Indicators of Hypertension. Endothelin-Related SNPs Are Currently in Clinical Trials." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2n4wa>.
 91. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bv. "Gingival and Intraventricular Haemorrhages Are Severe Newborn Diseases Causing Damage to White Matter and Neurological Dysfunction in Surviving Newborns Who Can Benefit from Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qb84p>.
 92. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bw. "Glioblastoma Therapeutic Approaches Were Established Utilizing Contemporary Discoveries in Delivering Medicines to the Brain as Smart Nanoparticles for Focused Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/db4f6>.
 93. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bx. "Haemophilia Gene Therapy Is in Clinical Studies, Making Continuous Safety and Efficacy Testing a Key Emphasis." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/sa8ny>.
 94. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021by. "Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation and Gene Therapy Are the Sole Treatments for Sickle Cell Disease and Other Hemoglobinopathies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/v8xqc>.
 95. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021bz. "Huntington's Disease Gene Therapy and Nanomedicines May Be Available Shortly." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/rxvgd>.
 96. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ca. "Hybrid Gene Therapy Designed to Fully Understand the Underlying Molecular Cancer Process May Be a Feasible Option." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ajyfd>.
 97. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cb. "Hydrogels Are Promising Considering Their Incredible Capacity to Modify, Encapsulate and Co-Deliver Medicinal Compounds, Cells, Biomolecules, and Nanomaterials." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/px3qy>.
 98. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cc. "Immune Evasion Is Linked to Histone Variation Malfunction. Gene Therapy Could Provide Tools for Targeting Histone Variant Deposition as a Critical Part of Its Pharmacology." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kjm76>.
 99. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cd. "Implementing the Human Artificial Chromosome Gene Therapy Platform Remains Challenging, but Continuous Animal Model Research Will Advance the Platform Closer to Clinical Trials." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/a53f7>.
 100. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ce. "Inflammatory Breast Cancer Remains the Most Aggressive Form of Breast Cancer. A Multimodality Therapeutic Plan Has Shown Improved Survival Results." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cr935>.
 101. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cf. "Inherited Immunohematological and Metabolic Diseases Have the Potential to Improve Significantly, or Be Cured, Using Haematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ukbnm>.
 102. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cg. "Insulin and IGF-1 Receptors Mutations Can Lead to Targets for Gene Therapy in Diabetes, Obesity, and Metabolic Syndrome." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/s86x5>.
 103. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ch. "Integrating High-Throughput Genetics and Neuroimaging Technologies

- Promises Greater Information on Neurobiological Anomalies in Neurodegenerative Diseases.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hpgyz>.
104. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ci. “Intravitreal and Subretinal Injections Currently Deliver Most Gene Therapy, Including siRNA for Eye Illnesses. Non-Viral Vectors May Provide Targeting.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/rjkhy>.
 105. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cj. “LncRNA Regulating Reprogramming Glucose Metabolism Has Become One of the Most Tempting Antineoplastic Targets for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/hqma5>.
 106. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ck. “lncRNAs Are Upregulated and Downregulated in OS Cells. Angiogenesis, Metastasis, Cell Signaling, Autophagy, and Death Are among Biological Processes That RNAs Play a Role in.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/48n7q>.
 107. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cl. “Magnetic Nanoparticles Are Widely Used in Drug Delivery, Imaging, Diagnosis, and Targeting. It Has Promises for the Treatment of Inflammatory Disorders such as Rheumatoid Arthritis.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/p2gme>.
 108. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cm. “Many miRNAs Participate in Inflammatory Regulation and Bone Metabolism. Overexpression of miR21 and miR155 Releases Proinflammatory Cytokines.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2wuvp>.
 109. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cn. “MiR490’s Diagnostic Capacity Was Demonstrated in Various Cancer Kinds and Diseases, Adding to Its Clinical Value.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wysre>.
 110. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021co. “miRNAs Have an Impact on Xeno-Infectious Diseases by Influencing Host And/or Infection Factors.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7qewx>.
 111. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cp. “Mutations in MED12 Lead to Mental Retardation, Including Opitz–Kaveggia Syndrome, Ohdo Syndrome, Lujan–Fryns Syndrome, and Psychosis. It’s a Target for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cyns8>.
 112. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cq. “Nanocarriers Can Be Used to Control the Activity of Genome Editing in a Spatiotemporal Way by Using Stimulusresponsive Nanocarriers.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/nua89>.
 113. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cr. “Nanomaterials Were Formed into Various Shapes, with Functionalization Aimed at Various Internalization Processes. Their Nanoscale Size Allows Drugs to Reach Cells or Extracellular Environments.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/p2ajv>.
 114. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cs. “Nanomedicine Is Offering Promising Strategies for Tumor Blockade Treatment.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/yzxuq>.
 115. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ct. “Network Medicine Might Lead to New Treatments for Dyslipidemia. It Will Be a Challenging Method to Implement in a Clinical Context.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/nksbw>.
 116. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cu. “Neuroinflammation Caused by Activated Microglia and Astrocytes Can Contribute to the Progression of Pathogenic Damage to Substantia Nigra Neurons, Playing a Role in Parkinson’s Disease Progression.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ac896>.
 117. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cv. “Neurologists Rarely Perform Genetic Testing for Parkinson’s Disease. Evidence Suggests That Many Patients with Major Genetic Variants Go Undiagnosed.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ykpb2>.
 118. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cw. “Neuronal Intranuclear Hyaline Inclusion Disease Is a Neurodegenerative Condition Which Can Be a Target for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/upgqd>.
 119. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cx. “New Therapies Aim at Restoring the Molecular, Morphological, and Functional Integrity of Parkinson’s Specific Brain Circuits.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dvyxc>.
 120. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cy. “Not All lncMIRHG’s Are ‘Junk Transcripts,’. LncM IRHG Loci May Make Both Functional miRNAs and lncRNAs, Which Can Work Together or Separately.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/a567w>.
 121. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021cz. “Nrf2 Signaling Pathways Are Part of a Wider Network of Signaling Pathways Regulating Thymoquinone Therapeutic Actions Which Need Innovative Formulations and Delivery Methods.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/u2fa7>.
 122. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021da. “Omics Should Be Integrated with Genomics to Uncover Molecular Networks and Tissue and Single-Cell Epigenetic Changes. With These Findings, Targeted Pseudoexfoliation Syndrome and Glaucoma Gene Therapy Procedures May Be Viable.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/48fj5>.
 123. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021db. “Ophthalmic Gene and Cell Therapies.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/n84m9>.
 124. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dc. “P21 Is a Flexible, Multi-Functional Protein. It Governs Various Tumor Cell Activities, Including Autophagy. p21 Is a Possible Radiotherapy Target.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ydkca>.

125. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dd. "Parkinson's Disease Simulating Complexity via Improving the Identification of Significant Genetic Alterations and Environmental Contaminants Should Be a Priority." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pmcu9>.
126. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021de. "Patient-Specific Microphysiology Systems Are Likely to Become a Crucial Aspect of Translational Research and Precision Medicine." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/bc8fr>.
127. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021df. "Patients with PMD Who Are Thoroughly Screened by Genomic Medicine Have a Considerable Chance of Benefiting Greatly from Whole-Genome Sequencing." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dajft>.
128. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dg. "Polydopamine Nanoparticles' Activity and Long-Term Stability Should Be Fully Studied for Gene Therapy Applications." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/x4nej>.
129. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dh. "Potential Therapeutics for Primary Mitochondrial Disorders." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6pz5k>.
130. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021di. "Potentials of Medicinal Nanostructured Diamond Particles and Coatings." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/h68xz>.
131. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dj. "Preclinical Investigations Revealed Possibilities for Salmonella Tumor Treatment. Bacteria Can Also Be Coupled to Nanomaterials Enabling Drug-Loading, Photocatalytic And/or Magnetic Properties, Using the Bacteria's Net Negative Charge." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/embqk>.
132. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dk. "Research into P2X Purinergic Receptor Function in Tumor Growth Has Made Substantial Progress with Potential Gene Therapy Targeting." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/r34fs>.
133. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dl. "RNA Therapies Hold Great Promise for Treating Cancer. High-Throughput Screening Techniques Have Facilitated the Development of RNA Treatments." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9vxrb>.
134. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dm. "RNAi Treatment Has Been Shown to Successfully Modify Human-Related Target Gene Expression, Including Cancer. It Has the Capacity to Control Non-Standard Oncogenes, such as Oncogenic lncRNAs." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/bwqep>.
135. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dn. "RNAs Hold a Lot of Potential When It Comes to Druggable Molecular Targets." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2dtxg>.
136. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021do. "Shadow Enhancers' Objective Seems to Be to Establish Robust Growth Patterns Independent of Genetic or Environmental Stress." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qfnkp>.
137. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dp. "Sickle Cell Disease Hematopoietic Stem Cell Gene Therapy with Globin Gene Addition Is Promising." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/j5fkb>.
138. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dq. "Single-Gene Mutations in mtDNA-Associated Proteins Are Unlikely to Be the Main Cause of Sporadic Parkinson's Disease. Cumulative Genetic Variation in Numerous Genes May Be Important in Neurodegeneration and PD Risk." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/89qte>.
139. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dr. "Small Nuclear Ribonucleoproteins (snRNPs) Based Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/c43r9>.
140. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ds. "Studying the Pathologic Mechanisms of Osteoporosis and the Bone Microenvironment May Help Researchers Better Know the Etiology of Rheumatoid Arthritis, Periodontitis, and Multiple Myeloma, as Well as Other Inflammatory and Autoimmune Disorders." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/t3z6y>.
141. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dt. "Suicide Gene Therapy May Be Effective in the Treatment of Malignant Glioma." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/vdkst>.
142. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021du. "Synuclein Is a Protein That Is Expressed in Brain Tissue. The Specific Missense Mutation (SNCA) Found in a Family with Parkinson's Disease Is the Cause. Other Diseases Include Alzheimer's Disease and REM Sleep Behavior Disorder." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/bs8rc>.
143. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dv. "Systems Biology Is a Method for Analyzing Massive Amounts of Multidimensional Data Generated by Omics Technologies. Cross-Validation of the Various Technological Platforms Is Critical." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/p8vkd>.
144. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dw. "Targeting Mitochondria and Especially Taz Gene Mutation Induces CL May Give Novel Therapeutic Alternatives for Treating Barth Syndrome." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/unfpy>.
145. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dx. "The Ability to Combine Multiple mRNA Antigens Targeting Multiple Pathogens Simultaneously, and the Robust Immune Responses Are Confirmed in Several Clinical Studies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6qksx>.
146. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dy. "The Cubic Polyhedral Oligomeric Silsesquioxanes Based Hybrid Materials Have a Wide Variety of Applications, Including Drug Administration, Gene Therapy,

- Biological Imaging, and Bone Regeneration.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9peq8>.
147. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021dz. “The Development of Tissue Replacement Therapies and Drug Discovery Was a Critical Milestone in Advancing Regenerative Medicine.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/w9bsm>.
 148. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ea. “The Epidemic of COVID-19 Prompted Widespread Use of mRNA Vaccinations.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/jqws5>.
 149. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eb. “The Most Useful and Commonly Available Acute Rejection Surveillance Strategies Are Routine Monitoring of Myocardial Function and Donor-Specific Anti-HLA Abs Monitoring.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ebw68>.
 150. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ec. “The Protease MBTPS2 Is an Important Regulator of Several Cellular Processes, Especially in Health and Sickness.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qyn6h>.
 151. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ed. “The Sigma 1 Receptor (S1R) Is a Potential Therapeutic Target for the Treatment of Huntington’s Disease.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mcefx>.
 152. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ee. “The Use of a Network Medicine Approach Might Result in Innovative Strategies for Lowering Coronary Heart Disease and CV Risks.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/eakg8>.
 153. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ef. “The Vasoconstrictor Endothelin System Involvement in Chronic Kidney Diseases Pathogenesis Is Now the Most Often Employed Treatment Method.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cnkqy>.
 154. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eg. “The VPS35-D620N Mutation Is Associated with Parkinson’s Disease and Can Be a Target for Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/83sxx>.
 155. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eh. “Therapeutics Including Gene Therapy for Osteoarthritis as a Concept.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7zsqq>.
 156. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ei. “Tissue Hypoxia Has Been Established as a Master Regulator for Alternative Splicing, with Substantial Clinical Consequences and Possibilities for Gene Therapy Targeting.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/5pbw4>.
 157. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ej. “To Rectify Alzheimer’s Disease Etiology, Excessive Mitochondrial Division Might Be Stopped or Mitophagy Might Be Promoted.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6kdxw>.
 158. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ek. “Transcriptomics Is a Rapidly Growing Field That Generates New Data That May Be Used on Its Own or in Combination with Existing Clinical Data for Development of New Therapeutics, Including Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kfr6a>.
 159. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021el. “Tumor Microenvironment Has Clinical Significance in Terms of Prognosis and Therapy Prediction.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4dz8q>.
 160. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021em. “Using AAV as a Gene Delivery Vector in the Neural System Is Effective in Several Animals, such as Nonhuman Primates.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ut4fa>.
 161. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021en. “Using Pre-Existing Datasets to Combine Published Information with New Metrics Would Help Researchers Construct a Broader Picture of Chromatin in Disease.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gsqv5>.
 162. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eo. “Virus-like Particles Are Good Nanocarriers for Liquid Biopsy Probes, Imaging Contrast Agents, and Anticancer Medications.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xbtka>.
 163. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ep. “ZEB1 Controls the Expression of ICAM1, Promoting Monocyte-Macrophage Adhesion and Hence the Formation of Atherosclerotic Lesions.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kzjqg>.
 164. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eq. “Gene Therapy Development and Legislation.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mwb2n>.
 165. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021er. “Next-Generation Sequencing Is Now Utilized to Identify Genetic Abnormalities and Develop Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/em7xp>.
 166. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021es. “Nucleic Acid Designs, Artificial Intelligence for Screening Nanomaterials, and Enhanced Characterization Methods Are Needed to Make Nanomedicine More Successful.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2w5aq>.
 167. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021et. “Potential Strategies for Cancer Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/atcqz>.
 168. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021eu. “Quantitative Groups Will Be Critical to the Success of Future Gene Therapy Programs.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/v97ht>.
 169. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ev. “The Treatment of Major Human Illnesses with Recombinant Adeno-Associated Virus (rAAV) Has Shown Tremendous Promises.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/uwa4e>.
 170. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ew. “Carbon Nanotubes Have Enormous Potential in Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9bcxk>.
 171. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ex. “Charge-Alteration-Based Approaches Can Address the Evolving Needs of Nucleic Acid-Based Gene Therapy, Charge Reversal Techniques Are Also Promising.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zwq5h>.

172. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ey. "Chromosome X, the Most Explored Genome-Editing Chromosome, Presents Possibilities for Hemophilia A Treatments." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6vsdz>.
173. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ez. "Clinical Investigations Show That siRNA May Be Used to Treat a Variety of Disorders, Including Cancer." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fcsgq>.
174. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fa. "Cyclodextrins as Potential Gene Therapy Vectors." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zhtsc>.
175. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fb. "Development of Specialized Carriers Capable of Delivering Effective RNAi and siRNA Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3ykwk>.
176. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fc. "Gene Therapy Can Target Mutations such as BRAF, Which Have Been Shown to Make Tumors More Susceptible to Autophagy Suppression." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3gwra>.
177. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fd. "Gene Therapy Vectors Should Enable CRISPR Systems to Accumulate at Disease Sites and Successfully Penetrate Nuclei." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xzmmc>.
178. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fe. "Nanoformulations Can Be Utilized to Deliver Effective siRNA to Tumor Cells to Decrease Gene Expression." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zvukc>.
179. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ff. "Neuronal Ceroid Lipofuscinosis Therapeutics." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/75vcp>.
180. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fg. "Nonviral Gene Delivery Vectors for Transfection of the CAR Gene for CAR-T Cell Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ckxh5>.
181. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fh. "Potential HIV Gene Therapy Strategies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/e5hm2>.
182. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fi. "Research on Cell Sources for Brain Cell Replacement Methods Has Gained Major Importance. Cell and Gene Therapy Are Potentially Intriguing New Domains of Regenerative Medicine." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/g835b>.
183. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fj. "RNAi-Based Gene Therapy Provides a Wide Variety of Applications. Safe, Biodegradable Nano Delivery Vectors Are Still Needed." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/s2zhn>.
184. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fk. "Strategies for Treating Multiple Sclerosis with Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/sync6>.
185. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fl. "The Combination of Unique Biomolecules and Nanoparticles Has Shown Successful Gene Therapy Treatment Approaches for Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer Treatment." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/yeq5z>.
186. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fm. "Understanding Why the Same Gene Delivery Vector Behaves Differently in Different Cell Types Is Essential for Developing More Adaptable Transfection Systems." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6q8af>.
187. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fn. "AAV9 Is Considered the Most Efficient AAV Serotype Targeting Blood-Brain Barriers. To Enhance Effective Gene Therapy for CNS Illnesses, Testing Novel Vectors with More Efficient Crossing Capabilities Is Vital." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7bf5s>.
188. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fo. "Artificial miRNAs Are Potential Gene Therapy Tools, Especially for Incurable Monogenic Disorders." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/d5rnm>.
189. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fp. "Breakthroughs in mRNA Modification and Nanoparticle-Based Delivery Vehicles Facilitate Gene Therapy Strategies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ky7dt>.
190. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fq. "CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Genome Editing Has Demonstrated Significant Promise for Genetic Correction in Autologous Hematopoietic Stem/progenitor Cells (HSPCs) and Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (iPSCs)." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xk54r>.
191. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fr. "Gene Therapy Vectors for Targeting the Heart." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gcbhf>.
192. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fs. "Liposomes Can Minimize Cardiotoxicity, Address Drug Resistance, and Improve Overall Drug Release Profiles in Breast Cancer." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tn56d>.
193. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ft. "Liposomes with Cerasome-Forming Lipids as Gene Therapy Vectors." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zjn6v>.
194. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fu. "Nanomaterials Combine Multiple Therapeutic Approaches for Cancer Cell Multidrug Resistance, Ferroptotic Cell Death Is Promising in Various Cancers." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7bg9t>.
195. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fv. "Nanomedicines for Enhanced Permeability and Retention (EPR)-Stratified Patients Have the Potential to Improve Treatment Outcomes." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xrcb2>.
196. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fw. "RNA-Based Gene Therapy for Manipulating the Neuroinflammatory Cascade Closely Linked to Neurodegeneration Can Help Reduce Disease Development." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2hswv>.
197. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fx. "Targeted Chemical Nucleases Have a Wide Range of Untapped Applications in Biological Fields, Including Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6bexs>.

198. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fy. "Bacterial Nanoparticles Can Deliver Proteins, Medications, Enzymes, and Genes to Diagnose and Cure Numerous Illnesses." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7gyna>.
199. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021fz. "Exosomal miRNA Diagnostic and Gene Therapy Tools." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/aknrc>.
200. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ga. "Gene Modification Research Has Potential, from Diagnostic to Therapeutic Levels. The Most Promising Metabolic Pathways Include the TGF-1 Signaling System, Inflammation and Protein Transport." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/5ert4>.
201. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gb. "Gene Therapy Using MnO₂ Nanoparticles." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xmwjs>.
202. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gc. "Gene-Regulatory Elements May Change the Amount, Timing, or Location of Gene Expression, Cis-Regulation Therapy Platforms Might Become a Gene Therapy to Treat Many Genetic Diseases." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xc5a2>.
203. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gd. "Hemophilia Therapeutics." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gu74x>.
204. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ge. "Mesenchymal Stem Cells Strategies in Cancer Immunotherapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dkv6w>.
205. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gf. "Nanomaterials Can Inhibit Planktonic and Biofilm Bacteria and Can Be Used as Topical Therapy for Mouth and Wound-Related Infections." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/aqd2e>.
206. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gg. "New Technologies to Improve CAR T Cell Generation and Biomanufacturing Will Lead to Safer, More Therapeutically Effective Cells." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/un8gp>.
207. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gh. "Ocular Gene Therapy Strategies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7en3k>.
208. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gi. "Peripheral Nerve Injury Therapeutics, Including Electrical Stimulation, Stem Cell Treatments, and Synthetic Neural Scaffolds, Have Shown Promising Preclinical and Even Clinical Results with Potential Regenerative Treatment." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m8cs9>.
209. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gj. "Photothermal and Photodynamic Photoactivation of Nanomaterials-Based Prodrugs Are Two Key Methods for NIR Light-Mediated Photoactivation." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2bh3r>.
210. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gk. "Quantum Dots Have the Potential to Be Used in Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/bdeg6>.
211. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gl. "Sickle Cell Disease Has Emerged as a Public Health Concern. Some Drugs May Conflict with Curative Therapies, yet They May Be Useful as a Bridge to HSCT and Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6kufh>.
212. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gm. "Stimulator of Interferon Genes (STING)-Activating Nanoparticles Can Be Employed as a Tool for Controlled Immune Activation." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2ez7a>.
213. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gn. "CRISPR/Cas9 Has Introduced New Gene Therapy Possibilities for Muscular Dystrophies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ug8v4>.
214. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021go. "Degradable Branched Polycationic Systems Are Promising Gene Therapy Vectors." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/utypf>.
215. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gp. "Developing Nanotechnology Platforms for Peptide-Based Combinatory Cancer Gene Therapy Will Likely Have a Significant Influence on the Development of Personalized Cancer Medicines." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zbrkj>.
216. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gq. "Exosomes May Prevent Cardiac Attacks, Heart Failure, and Cardiomyopathy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/agm3k>.
217. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gr. "Exosomes Potential Therapeutics." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/mhwt3>.
218. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gs. "Gene Therapy Using miRNA Treatment Suppresses the Expression of Bone-Forming Defective Genes and Raises the Expression of Genes That Become Dormant during Bone Building." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tcka3>.
219. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gt. "Genome-Editing Is Promising for Producing Therapeutically Relevant Animal Models for Possible Therapies for Rare Human Diseases." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/dehr9>.
220. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gu. "Human Corneal Endothelial Cells Grafts to Replace Cadaveric Donor Corneas." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/p9x7e>.
221. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gv. "Hybrid Nanotechnology and Peptide Nucleic Acid Could Improve the Effectiveness of Gene Therapy by Increasing Its Cell Permeability." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/d8wzt>.
222. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gw. "In Prenatal Stem Cell Transplantation and in Utero Gene Therapy, a Wide Spectrum of Genetic Diseases Can Be Diagnosed and Treated before Birth." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/sa3vz>.
223. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gx. "Magnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles Have Potential on Gene Therapy

- Effectiveness and Biocompatibility.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/f3hm4>.
224. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gy. “Neurotrophin Gene Therapy May Be Able to Treat Individuals with Noise-Induced Hearing Loss or Neural Presbycusis.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/spkxh>.
225. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021gz. “Plant Viral Nanoparticles Can Be Used in Biological Systems for Loading and Transporting Cargo.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/txdka>.
226. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021ha. “Polydopamine May Be Easily Functionalized with a Range of Nanomaterials for Synergistic Cancer Therapy, in Addition to Its Exceptional Photothermal Effects.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/cq942>.
227. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021hb. “Tumor-Targeted Drug Delivery Systems for Anticancer Therapies Can Selectively Provide an Appropriate Cytotoxic Payload to Cancer Cells, Reducing the Side Effects of Chemo.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/683nj>.
228. Moataz Dowaidar. n.d. “Guidelines for the Use and Interpretation of Assays for Monitoring Autophagy (4th Edition).”
229. Dowaidar, Moataz, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Krista Freimann, Kaido Kurrikoff, Xiaodong Zou, and Ülo Langel. 2017. “Magnetic Nanoparticle Assisted Self-Assembly of Cell Penetrating Peptides-Oligonucleotides Complexes for Gene Delivery.” *Scientific Reports* 7 (1): 9159. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-09803-z>.
230. Dowaidar, Moataz, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Ülo Langel, and Xiaodong Zou. 2018. “Supplemental Material for Chitosan Enhances Gene Delivery of Oligonucleotide Complexes with Magnetic Nanoparticles–cell-Penetrating Peptide.” *SAGE Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.25384/SAGE.7105436.V1>.
231. Dowaidar, Moataz, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Xiaodong Zou, and Ülo Langel. 2017a. “Graphene Oxide Nanosheets in Complex with Cell Penetrating Peptides for Oligonucleotides Delivery General Subjects.” *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta, General Subjects*. <https://pubag.nal.usda.gov/catalog/5734174>.
232. Moataz Dowaidar. 2017b. “Graphene Oxide Nanosheets in Complex with Cell Penetrating Peptides for Oligonucleotides Delivery.” *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta, General Subjects* 1861 (9): 2334–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2017.07.002>.
233. Dowaidar, Moataz, and Moataz Dowaidar. 2018. “Chimeric Gene Delivery Vectors : Design, Synthesis, and Mechanisms from Transcriptomics Analysis.”
234. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021a. “Addiction Biology Research on miRNAs, and Their Role in the Pathophysiology of Addiction Is Enabling Gene Therapy Opportunities.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/z5wyt>.
235. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021b. “Aptamers Targeting Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor Molecular Regulation as Potential Therapists.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/a8qpr>.
236. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021c. “Arrhythmogenic Cardiomyopathy Is a Set of Hereditary Cardiac Muscle Disorders Where Various Etiologies Converge. Most ACM Patients Do Not Have a Genetic Diagnosis.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pzvtv3>.
237. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021d. “Autophagy, Immunological Response, and Inflammation All Rely on the TRIM Family Proteins. TRIM-Based Therapeutics for Inflammatory Illnesses Including Diabetes and Diabetic Comorbidities Are Promising.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/y4g6e>.
238. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021e. “Biogenic Particles Can Be Multiantigenic, Immunostimulative and Activate Innate Immunity While Suppressing Tumor Development.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/q2kby>.
239. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021f. “Biological Medications for Interventional Pain Have a Lot of Clinical Data behind Them. It Is Fair to Assume They Will Replace Steroid-Based Interventional Techniques, Providing Patients with Longer Relief.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4y5fm>.
240. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021g. “Carbon Nanofibers Assist in the Manufacture of Prosthetic Joints, Promote Tissue, Organ, Nerve Regeneration and Development, and Improve Anticancer Therapy Impact and Chemosensitization for a Range of Tumor Types.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/z3ucn>.
241. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021h. “Emerging Therapy Options May Help Patients with RAG Deficiency, Especially Those with Severe Immune Dysregulation.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/v5tjg>.
242. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021i. “Exosomes as Promising Gene Therapy Tools Still Need to Be Researched and Manufactured More Efficiently.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/nw4z7>.
243. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021j. “Focus on Exosomes Could Help Make the Use of Circulating miRNA as Biomarkers More Practical. A Detailed Understanding of miRNA Behavior Should Be a Subject of Gene Therapy.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/uan6x>.
244. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021k. “Gene-Free Viral-like Particles (VLPs) Offer a Safer Alternative to Inactivating or Weakening Viral Strains for Traditional Vaccines. VLP-Based Vaccinations without Adjuvants Have Been Found to Promote Humoral and Cellular Immunity.” <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9dvut>.

245. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021l. "Given the Importance of mTOR Signaling in a Number of Illnesses, It Looks Suitable to Use miR 99 Family Members as a Therapeutic Intervention to Deal with These Illnesses by Using Gene Therapy Tools." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8cwgh>.
246. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021m. "HMGB1 Has Sparked a Lot of Attention as a Model DAMP Molecule Involved in Inflammation, Inflammatory Diseases, and Cancer." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/5qx36>.
247. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021n. "Nucleic Acid Nanocarriers Can Be Programmable, Spatially Adjustable and Biocompatible, Minimizing Systemic Toxicity and Improving Pharmacodynamics." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wr237>.
248. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021o. "Osteoporosis Is a Prominent Source of Morbidity and Mortality in the Elderly, Particularly in Postmenopausal Women. Long Noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs) Have Been Found to Be Important Regulators and Possible Gene Therapy Targets." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ghfpt>.
249. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021p. "Polycomb Genes Role in Cancer Pathophysiology Is Offering Targets for Therapeutics Including Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/sfvej>.
250. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021q. "RNA Sequencing and Microarray Analysis Are Helpful Techniques to Detect Obesity-Related lncRNAs. lncRNA Can Alter Cholesterol Metabolism and Can Be a Target for Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/3fb6w>.
251. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021r. "Sepsis-Associated Acute Kidney Damage Is a Disease That Affects the Patient's Quality of Life. It Should Be a Target for Gene Therapy." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/49k7q>.
252. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021s. "The Gene Expression Profiling Gives an in-Depth Insight of Breast Cancer Heterogeneity, Better than a Single Protein or Gene Expression. It Is Time to Include It in the Daily Routine." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xhyd7>.
253. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021t. "The Nanomedicine System Has Successfully Inhibited Tumor Neovascularization Using Gene Silencing, Chemotherapy, Photothermal Therapy, and Other Therapies." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/rk2bf>.
254. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021u. "The Therapeutic Application of a Nucleic Acid Sequence to Patients' Diseased Organs Is Currently Available." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pqsbf>.
255. Moataz Dowaidar. 2021v. "Triple-Negative Breast Cancer, Which Lacks the Expression of Hormone Receptors and HER2, Has a Worse Prognosis. Massive Parallel Sequencing Is Capable of Reliably Breaking down the Intra-Tumor and Inter-Tumor Heterogeneity." <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pvk7u>.
256. Dowaidar, Moataz, H. A. Ismail, A. A. Alghasham, M. M. Dowaidar, and A. A. Settin. 2011. "Polymorphisms in MTHF and Ace Genes and the Association with Hypertension among Saudi Population from Qassim Region." *Egyptian Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 29 (1). <https://doi.org/10.4314/ejbmb.v29i1.67382>.
257. Dowaidar, Moataz, Hani Nasser Abdelhamid, Mattias Hällbrink, Ülo Langel, and Xiaodong Zou. 2018. "Chitosan Enhances Gene Delivery of Oligonucleotide Complexes with Magnetic Nanoparticles-Cell-Penetrating Peptide." *Journal of Biomaterials Applications* 33 (3): 392–401. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885328218796623>.
258. Dowaidar, Moataz, and Ahmad Settin. 2010. "Risk of Myocardial Infarction Related to Factor V Leiden Mutation: A Meta-Analysis." *Genetic Testing and Molecular Biomarkers* 14 (4): 493–98. <https://doi.org/10.1089/gtmb.2010.0017>.
259. Gestin, Maxime, Moataz Dowaidar, and Ülo Langel. 2017. "Uptake Mechanism of Cell-Penetrating Peptides." *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology* 1030: 255–64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66095-0_11.
260. Ismail, H. A., A. A. Alghasham, M. M. Dowaidar, and A. A. Settin. 2011. "Polymorphisms in MTHF and Ace Genes and the Association with Hypertension among Saudi Population from Qassim Region." *Egyptian Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 29 (1). <https://doi.org/10.4314/ejbmb.v29i1.67382>.
261. Settin, Ahmad A., Abdullah Algasham, Moataz Dowaidar, and Hisham Ismail. 2009. "Methylene Tetrahydrofolate Reductase and Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Gene Polymorphisms Related to Overweight/obesity among Saudi Subjects from Qassim Region." *Disease Markers* 27 (2): 97–102. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DMA-2009-0660>.
262. Settin, Ahmad A., Abdullah Alghasham, Ahmad Ali, Moataz Dowaidar, and Hisham Ismail. 2012. "Frequency of Thrombophilic Genetic Polymorphisms among Saudi Subjects Compared with Other Populations." *Hematology* 17 (3): 176–82. <https://doi.org/10.1179/102453312X13376952196575>.
263. Settin, Ahmad, Ibrahim S. Abu-Saif, Rizk El-Baz, Moataz Dowaidar, Rabab Abu-Al Kasim, and Shaimaa Shabana. 2007a. "Diagnosis of Sex Chromosome Disorders and Prenatal Diagnosis of Down Syndrome Using Interphase Fluorescent In-Situ Hyperidization Technique." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 1 (2): 203–9. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21475429>.

264. Settin, Ahmad, Abdullah Algasham, Moataz Dowaidar, and Hisham Ismail. 2011. "Methylene Tetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) and Angiotensinogen Converting Enzyme (ACE) Gene Polymorphisms Related to Overweight and Obesity among Saudi Patients in Al Qassim." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 5 (2 Suppl 1): 24–25. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23284565>.
265. Settin, Ahmad, Hala Almarsafawy, Ahmad Alhussieny, and Moataz Dowaidar. 2008a. "Dysmorphic Features, Consanguinity and Cytogenetic Pattern of Congenital Heart Diseases: A Pilot Study from Mansoura Locality, Egypt." *International Journal of Health Sciences* 2 (2): 101–11. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21475491>.
266. Settin, Ahmad, Moataz Dowaidar, Rizk El-Baz, Ayman Abd-Al-Samad, Ibrahim El-Sayed, and Mahmoud Nasr. 2008. "Frequency of Factor V Leiden Mutation in Egyptian Cases with Myocardial Infarction." *Hematology* 13 (3): 170–74. <https://doi.org/10.1179/102453308X316158>.
267. Venit, Tomas, Moataz Dowaidar, Maxime Gestin, Syed Raza Mahmood, Ülo Langel, and Piergiorgio Percipalle. 2020. "Transcriptional Profiling Reveals Ribosome Biogenesis, Microtubule Dynamics and Expression of Specific lncRNAs to Be Part of a Common Response to Cell-Penetrating Peptides." *Biomolecules* 10 (11): 1567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10111567>.